

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PROBLEM OF ILLEGAL MIGRATION AND HUMAN TRAFFICKING

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Abstract: This article analyzes that today illegal migration and human trafficking are a problem of serious concern to many countries. It is also highlighted that irregular and illegal movement of people is the main factor of illegal migration.

Key words: migration, illegal migration, human trafficking, slavery, torture.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda noqonuniy migratsiya va odam savdosi ko'plab mamlakatlarni jiddiy tashvishga solayotgan muammo ekanligi tahlil etilgan. Shuningdek, insonlarning artibsiz holda noqonuniy tarzda harakatlarni noqonuniy migratsiyaning asosiy omili ekanligi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: migratsiya, noqonuniy migratsiya, odam savdosi, qullik, qiynoq.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется, что сегодня нелегальная миграция и торговля людьми являются проблемой, вызывающей серьезную обеспокоенность многих стран. Также подчеркивается, что нерегулярное и незаконное перемещение людей является основным фактором нелегальной миграции.

Ключевые слова: миграция, нелегальная миграция, торговля людьми, рабство, пытки.

INTRODUCTION

Migration is a very ancient phenomenon, a process that includes several situations that lead to a change in the place of residence of the population. To date, the development of this process in the framework of various disciplines and directions is scientifically studied.

As the society develops and progresses, migration becomes a socio-economic necessity and becomes a habit. That is why migration is a very complex social process, which includes many areas of the socio-economic and cultural life of the population.

In the 21st century, the scale of migration is growing and its geography is expanding. The widespread development of migration in the current integration processes leads to the development of international migration and an increase in the number of international migrants. Article 13 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states: “Everyone has the right to freedom of movement and residence within any state. Everyone has the right to leave any country, especially his own country, and to return to his own country” [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Russian demographer and economist L.L. Rybakovskiy in his monograph entitled “Migration nasele-niya: prognozy, faktori, politika” defines the term migration as “territorial movement of people for different purposes and for different periods of time” [2].

The movement of migrants, in turn, causes the development of international migration, one of the current trends in international migration is the growth of illegal migration [3].

In recent years, the development of illegal migration has become one of the global problems. The main reason for this is the irregular and illegal movement of people in the wide-ranging and multifaceted population migration. Migrant movement is a constant movement from a certain point and return to the starting point with seasonal and pendulum movement. Illegal migration in the category of global problems can seriously threaten the international community and international stability. Because illegal migration includes illegal migrant workers, asylum seekers, and refugees. People migrate in order to feed their families, improve their financial situation, housing, change their lifestyle, and earn material income.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the same time that today's globalization processes are rapidly progressing, the increase of illegal migrants, human rights, health, household services, their disconnection from their own country, disconnection from the Eastern spiritual and moral roots, human trafficking, premature we should not forget that it brought out negative aspects such as death, being cheated without getting the right salary for one's work ^[4].

In fact, the possibility of becoming a victim of human trafficking is very high for those who seek work abroad illegally, because human trafficking is now mostly directly related to illegal migration. As a result of the involvement of unemployed women in religious and political movements through financial incentives through various fraudulent means, it was found that 1 thousand 934 women in Uzbekistan in 2007, of which 472 in Namangan region and 347 in Fergana region, fell into this situation ^[5].

In 2008, more than 1,000 people were victims of human trafficking crimes in Uzbekistan, 35-40% of them were women, and 10-15% were children. By the end of the first three months of 2010, 81 citizens were injured in the crime of human trafficking, 6 of them were women, 75 were men, and 1 was a minor. Most of the victims were from the Russian Federation (41 people) and the Republic of Kazakhstan (31 people). The involvement of women in human trafficking has led to the deepening of this issue ^[6].

It should be emphasized that human trafficking has a disgusting appearance, as it violates a person's life, freedom, and rights, trampling on his will, destiny, and future. Also, it is worrying that most of the migrants who went abroad to look for work illegally face difficult working conditions, unsanitary lifestyle, and various infectious diseases are recorded among them. During 2015, 425 thousand 487 migrants were tested for HIV infection in all regions of the republic according to their places of residence, 491 of them were diagnosed with HIV infection ^[7]. Based on the medical observation of HIV-positive migrants, regional Women's and Girls', neighborhood and health departments carried out preventive measures to prevent the spread of the disease among their family members.

Unfortunately, we are facing some new social problems in the conditions where the development of humanity is reaching new levels. Humanity has fought against slavery for hundreds of years was able to abolish slavery. Unfortunately, slavery is modern appearances appeared. Human trafficking is the modern form of slavery. Unfortunately, the victims of this disease are mainly women and children. Criminal groups have made a habit of using women and children for the most heinous purposes ^[8]. By the end of the 20th century, cases such as slavery, selling women as living goods, forcing them to commit sexual violence, and exploitation in order to gain material wealth became stronger. For this reason, the fight against this process is gaining international importance. The reason is that women's trafficking is an international crime that has a great negative impact on the gene pool of the entire humanity and nation. According to the data of the International Labor Organization in 2017, 24.9 million people worldwide became victims of human trafficking this year. 16 million of them were forced to work in the private sector, and 4.8 million women were living victims of sexual exploitation ^[9]. Women's traffic also becomes important in migration due to the reduction of legal migration or the existence of several restrictions on it, the illegal crossing of the border in order to earn economic income, and because of this, women migrants are deceived, and as a result, they face various difficulties. As a result of exploitation, women's rights are violated. Every year, 600,000 to 800,000 women and children are taken to foreign countries and sold as slaves by various means of deception ^[10]. Millions of women in the world experience torture, violence, hunger, poverty, discrimination, slavery, and exploitation every day. According to UN data, about 2,700,000 people worldwide become victims of human trafficking every year. More than 90 percent of them are women and children. Women face various difficulties and problems due to illegal migration. In particular, he is subject to harassment and violence. As a result, their dignity is valued and exploited by third parties.

"Agreement on cooperation in the fight against illegal migration" was adopted by the CIS member states on March 6, 1998. In this legal document, "Through the territories of the parties a third person who violates the rules of entry, exit, stay or transit citizens or stateless persons, as well as established in the territory of one of the parties in its national legislation citizens who violated the rules of stay" are illegal migrants calculation is reflected.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to further improve the system of combating human trafficking and forced labor” adopted on June 30, 2019, the Republican Interagency Committee on Combating Human Trafficking The commission was reorganized into the National Commission to Combat Human Trafficking and Forced Labor headed by the Chairman of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis.

CONCLUSION

The Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan pays great attention to the issues of protection of labor migrants – citizens of our country abroad, as well as assistance to victims of human trafficking and helpless migrants. About combating human trafficking and illegal migration “Are you being invited to work abroad? Don’t be fooled!”, “Don’t agree to slavery”, “Consequences of illegal migration”, “Let’s unite to fight human trafficking”, “Reminders for those going abroad” educational seminars and trainings, round talks, open discussions, actions in progress. The adoption of the Law “On Combating Human Trafficking” of the Republic of Uzbekistan serves as an effective means of protecting the dignity and worth of a person from criminal attacks.

List of references:

1. Universal Declaration of Human Rights.-T.: “Uzbekistan”, 2008.
2. Rybakovsky L.L. “Migration to the United States: prognosis, factors, politics”. – M.: “Nauka” 1987, B.5
3. Legal encyclopedia of Uzbekistan / Responsible for publication: Muhitdinov R.A. and others. / Responsible editor: Toychiyev N. – Tashkent.: Adolat, 2011. – B.307.
4. Hayitov Sh. Theoretical methodological analysis of migration processes at the current stage. Republic-wide online scientific-practical conference on current problems of world history Republican materials on the subject. Bukhara-2020.P-328.
5. Current archive of the Women’s Committee of Uzbekistan, data of 2007.
6. Own MA, M. Fund 170, list 1, collective volume 86, sheets 168-173.
7. Own MA, M. Fund 170, list 1, collection volume 209, page 24.
8. Matkarimova G., A. Alimov. Human trafficking: problems and solutions. T – 2017. 3 p.
9. www.ilo.org.
10. Kadirov R. Human trafficking is a global problem // Xalq so’zi, 2008, October 17.
11. Azamatova, G. B. (2022, June). The Republic Of Uzbekistan And South Korea: Mutually Beneficial Cooperation In The Field Of Labor Migration. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 60-65).
12. Azamatova, G. B. (2024). Characteristics Of Development Of Population Migration In Independent Uzbekistan // Экономика и социум, (2 (117)-1), 109-112.
13. Azamatova, G. (2021). Illegal Migration And Human Trafficking. Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government, 27(2), 3541-3545.
14. Azamatova, G. B. (2022). Some Considerations On The Migration Movements Of The Population Of Jizzah Region And Its Periodic Change. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 2(12), 09-13.

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